

Exploring Neutrosophic Contra Alpha Generalized Semi-Continuous Maps

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Abstract. In this manuscript, we have introduced the concepts of contra alpha generalized semi-continuous mapping and contra alpha semi-irresolute mapping within the Neutrosophic framework. Furthermore, we have derived certain properties associated with these mappings.

Keywords: Neutrosophic contra α -generalized semi- continuous mapping; Neutrosophic contra α -generalized semi-irresolute mapping

1. Introduction

Dontchev [1] initially proposed the notion of contra-continuity, while Jafari and Noiri [3] introduced novel extensions of contra-continuity termed contra- α -continuity in the context of topological spaces. In 2006, Ekici and Etienne Kerre [4] introduced contra-continuous mapping in the domain of fuzzy topological spaces. Additionally, Kresteska and Ekici introduced the concept of intuitionistic fuzzy contra-continuous mapping.

2. Neutrosophic contra α -generalized semi continuous mappings

Definition 2.1. A mapping $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s)$ is called a Neutrosophic contra α -generalized semi continuous ($\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous in short) mapping if $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(\hat{E}_{22}^*)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $(\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^t)$ for every $\hat{N}_{eut}CS \hat{E}_{22}^*$ of $(\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s)$.

Example 2.2. Let $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}} = \{a_1^*, a_2^*\}$, $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}} = \{a_3^*, a_4^*\}$, $\hat{E}_{11}^* = \langle x, (\frac{7}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{10}), (\frac{4}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{10}) \rangle$ and $\hat{E}_{22}^* = \langle y, (\frac{1}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{4}{5}), (\frac{1}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{9}{10}) \rangle$. Then $\hat{N}_{eut}^t = \{0_{\hat{N}_{eut}}, \hat{E}_{11}^*, 1_{\hat{N}_{eut}}\}$ and $\hat{N}_{eut}^s = \{0_{\hat{N}_{eut}}, \hat{E}_{22}^*, 1_{\hat{N}_{eut}}\}$

are $\dot{N}_{eut}Ts$ on $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$ respectively. Define a mapping $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^s)$ by $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_1^*) = a_3^*$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_2^*) = a_4^*$. Then \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Theorem 2.3. *Every Neutrosophic contra continuous mapping is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping .*

Proof. Let $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^s)$ be a Neutrosophic contra continuous mapping. Let \hat{E}_{11}^* be a $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$. By hypothesis, $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(\hat{E}_{11}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}OS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Since every $\dot{N}_{eut}OS$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$, $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(\hat{E}_{11}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Hence \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Example 2.4. $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous $\not\rightarrow$ Neutrosophic contra continuous.

Let $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}} = \{a_1^*, a_2^*\}$, $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}} = \{a_3^*, a_4^*\}$, $\hat{E}_{11}^* = \langle x, (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{7}{10}), (\frac{1}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{9}{10}) \rangle$ and $\hat{E}_{22}^* = \langle y, (\frac{4}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{5}), (\frac{9}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{10}) \rangle$. Then $\dot{N}_{eut}^t = \{0_{\dot{N}_{eut}}, \hat{E}_{11}^*, 1_{\dot{N}_{eut}}\}$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^s = \{0_{\dot{N}_{eut}}, \hat{E}_{22}^*, 1_{\dot{N}_{eut}}\}$ are $\dot{N}_{eut}Ts$ on $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$ respectively. Define a mapping $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^s)$ by $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_1^*) = a_3^*$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_2^*) = a_4^*$. Then \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping. But \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} is not a $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$ contra continuous mapping. Since $\hat{E}_{22}^{*c} = \langle y, (\frac{1}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{4}{5}), (\frac{1}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{9}{10}) \rangle$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$ but $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(\hat{E}_{22}^{*c}) = \langle x, (\frac{1}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{4}{5}), (\frac{1}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{9}{10}) \rangle$ is not a $\dot{N}_{eut}OS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$.

Theorem 2.5. *Every $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha$ continuous mapping is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping .*

Proof. Let $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^s)$ be a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha$ continuous mapping. Let \hat{E}_{11}^* be a $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$. Then by hypothesis $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(\hat{E}_{11}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha OS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Since every $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha OS$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$, $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(\hat{E}_{11}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Hence \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Example 2.6. $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping $\not\rightarrow$ $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha$ continuous mapping.

Let $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}} = \{a_1^*, a_2^*\}$, $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}} = \{a_3^*, a_4^*\}$, $\hat{E}_{11}^* = \langle x, (\frac{1}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{9}{10}), (\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}) \rangle$ and $\hat{E}_{22}^* = \langle y, (1, \frac{1}{2}, 0), (\frac{7}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{10}) \rangle$. Then $\dot{N}_{eut}^t = \{0_{\dot{N}_{eut}}, \hat{E}_{11}^*, 1_{\dot{N}_{eut}}\}$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^s = \{0_{\dot{N}_{eut}}, \hat{E}_{22}^*, 1_{\dot{N}_{eut}}\}$ are $\dot{N}_{eut}Ts$ on X and Y respectively. Define a mapping $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^s)$ by $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_1^*) = a_3^*$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_2^*) = a_4^*$. Then \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping. But \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} is not a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha$ continuous mapping. Since $\hat{E}_{22}^{*c} = \langle y, (0, \frac{1}{2}, 1), (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{7}{10}) \rangle$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$ but $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(\hat{E}_{22}^{*c}) = \langle x, (0, \frac{1}{2}, 1), (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{7}{10}) \rangle$ is not a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha OS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Therefore \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping but not a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha$ continuous mapping.

Remark 2.7. $\dot{N}_{eut}C\gamma$ continuous mapping and $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping are independent of each other.

Example 2.8. $\dot{N}_{eut}C\gamma$ continuous mapping $\not\rightarrow$ $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Let $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}} = \{a_1^*, a_2^*\}$, $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}} = \{a_3^*, a_4^*\}$, $\hat{E}_{11}^* = \langle x, (\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}), (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{7}{10}) \rangle$ and $\hat{E}_{22}^* = \langle y, (\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}), (\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}) \rangle$. Then $\dot{N}_{eut}^t = \{0_{\dot{N}_{eut}}, \hat{E}_{11}^*, 1_{\dot{N}_{eut}}\}$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^s = \{0_{\dot{N}_{eut}}, \hat{E}_{22}^*, 1_{\dot{N}_{eut}}\}$

are $\dot{N}_{eut}Ts$ on $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$ respectively. Define a mapping $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^s)$ by $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_1^*) = a_3^*$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_2^*) = a_4^*$. Since $E_{22}^{*c} = \langle y, (\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}), (\frac{3}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{5}) \rangle$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$ but $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(E_{22}^{*c}) = \langle x, (\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}), (\frac{3}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{5}) \rangle$ is not a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Therefore \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\gamma$ continuous mapping but not a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Example 2.9. $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping $\not\rightarrow \dot{N}_{eut}C\gamma$ continuous mapping.

Let $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}} = \{a_1^*, a_2^*\}$, $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}} = \{a_3^*, a_4^*\}$, $E_{11}^* = \langle x, (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{7}{10}), (\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}) \rangle$, $E_{22}^* = \langle x, (\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}), (\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}) \rangle$ and $E_{33}^* = \langle y, (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{7}{10}), (\frac{3}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{5}) \rangle$. Then $\dot{N}_{eut}^t = \{0_{\dot{N}_{eut}}, E_{11}^*, E_{22}^*, 1_{\dot{N}_{eut}}\}$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^s = \{0_{\dot{N}_{eut}}, E_{33}^*, 1_{\dot{N}_{eut}}\}$ are $\dot{N}_{eut}Ts$ on $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$ respectively. Define a mapping $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^s)$ by $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_1^*) = a_3^*$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_2^*) = a_4^*$. Since $E_{33}^{*c} = \langle y, (\frac{7}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{10}), (\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}) \rangle$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in Y but $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(E_{33}^{*c}) = \langle x, (\frac{7}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{10}), (\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}) \rangle$ is not a $\dot{N}_{eut}\gamma OS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Therefore \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping but not a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\gamma$ continuous mapping.

Remark 2.10. $\dot{N}_{eut}CP$ continuous mapping and $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping are independent of each other.

Example 2.11. $\dot{N}_{eut}CP$ continuous mapping $\not\rightarrow \dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Let $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}} = \{a_1^*, a_2^*\}$, $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}} = \{a_3^*, a_4^*\}$, $E_{11}^* = \langle x, (\frac{1}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{7}{10}), (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}) \rangle$ and $E_{22}^* = \langle y, (\frac{1}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{4}{5}), (\frac{1}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{7}{10}) \rangle$. Then $\dot{N}_{eut}^t = \{0_{\dot{N}_{eut}}, E_{11}^*, 1_{\dot{N}_{eut}}\}$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^s = \{0_{\dot{N}_{eut}}, E_{22}^*, 1_{\dot{N}_{eut}}\}$ are $\dot{N}_{eut}Ts$ on $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$ respectively.

Define a mapping $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^s)$ by $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_1^*) = a_3^*$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_2^*) = a_4^*$. Then \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping. But \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} is not a $\dot{N}_{eut}CP$ continuous mapping. Since $E_{22}^{*c} = \langle y, (\frac{4}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{10}), (\frac{7}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{10}) \rangle$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$ but $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(E_{22}^{*c}) = \langle x, (\frac{1}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{7}{10}), (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}) \rangle$ is not a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$.

Example 2.12. $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping $\not\rightarrow \dot{N}_{eut}CP$ continuous mapping.

Let $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}} = \{a_1^*, a_2^*\}$, $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}} = \{a_3^*, a_4^*\}$, $E_{11}^* = \langle x, (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{7}{10}), (\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}) \rangle$, $E_{22}^* = \langle x, (\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}), (\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}) \rangle$ and $E_{33}^* = \langle y, (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{7}{10}), (\frac{3}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{2}{5}) \rangle$. Then $\dot{N}_{eut}^t = \{0_{\dot{N}_{eut}}, E_{11}^*, E_{22}^*, 1_{\dot{N}_{eut}}\}$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^s = \{0_{\dot{N}_{eut}}, E_{33}^*, 1_{\dot{N}_{eut}}\}$ are $\dot{N}_{eut}Ts$ on $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$ respectively. Define a mapping $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^s)$ by $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_1^*) = a_3^*$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_2^*) = a_4^*$. Since $E_{33}^{*c} = \langle y, (\frac{7}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{10}), (\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}) \rangle$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in Y but $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(E_{33}^{*c}) = \langle x, (\frac{7}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{10}), (\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}) \rangle$ is not a $\dot{N}_{eut}POS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Therefore \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping but not a $\dot{N}_{eut}CP$ continuous mapping.

Theorem 2.13. A mapping $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} : \dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}} \rightarrow \dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}CaGS$ continuous if and only if the inverse image of each $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}OS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}\alpha GSCS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$.

Proof. Necessary Part: Let E_{11}^* be a $\dot{N}_{eut}OS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$. This implies E_{11}^{*c} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$. Since \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping, $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(E_{11}^{*c})$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$.

Since $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(E_{11}^{*c}) = (\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(E_{11}^*))^c$, $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(E_{11}^*)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}$.

Sufficient Part: Let E_{11}^* be a $\hat{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Y}}$. This implies E_{11}^{*c} is a $\hat{N}_{eut}OS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Y}}$. By hypothesis, $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(E_{11}^{*c})$ is $\hat{N}_{eut}G\alpha GSCS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}$. Since $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(E_{11}^{*c}) = (\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(E_{11}^*))^c$, $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(E_{11}^*)$ is $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}$. Hence \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Theorem 2.14. Let $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s)$ be a mapping and let $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(E_{11}^{*c})$ be a $\hat{N}_{eut}ROS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}$ for every $\hat{N}_{eut}CS$ E_{11}^* in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Y}}$. Then \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Proof. Let E_{11}^* be a $\hat{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Y}}$. Then by hypothesis, $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(E_{11}^{*c})$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}ROS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}$. Since every $\hat{N}_{eut}ROS$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$, $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(E_{11}^{*c})$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}$. Hence \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Theorem 2.15. Let $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s)$ be a $\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping, then \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a Neutrosophic contra continuous mapping if $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha gaT_{1/2}$ space.

Proof. Let E_{11}^* be a $\hat{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Y}}$. Then by hypothesis $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(E_{11}^*)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}$. Since $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha gaT_{1/2}$ space, $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(E_{11}^*)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}OS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}$. Hence \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a Neutrosophic contra continuous mapping.

Theorem 2.16. Let $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s)$ be a $\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping and $\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Z}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^d)$ is a Neutrosophic contra continuous mapping, then $(\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*}) : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Z}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^d)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Proof. Let E_{11}^* be a $\hat{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Z}}$. Then by hypothesis, $\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*^{-1}}(E_{11}^*)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}OS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Y}}$. Since \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping, $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*^{-1}}(E_{11}^*))$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}$. That is $(\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(E_{11}^*)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}$. Hence $(\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*})$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Theorem 2.17. Let $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s)$ be a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GS$ continuous mapping and $\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Z}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^d)$ is a Neutrosophic contra continuous mapping, then $\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Z}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^d)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Proof. Let E_{11}^* be a $\hat{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Z}}$. Then $\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*^{-1}}(E_{11}^*)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}OS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Y}}$, by hypothesis. Since \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GS$ continuous mapping, $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*^{-1}}(E_{11}^*))$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}$. That is $(\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(E_{11}^*)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}$. Hence $(\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*})$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Theorem 2.18. $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s)$ and $\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{Z}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^d)$ be mappings. Then the given conditions are equivalent if $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\hat{X}}$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha gaT_{1/2}$ space.

- (1) $\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*}$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

(2) $\dot{N}_{eut-cl}(\dot{N}_{eut-int}(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(B)) \subseteq (\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*)$ for every $\dot{N}_{eut}OS E_{22}^*$ in Z .

Proof. (1) \Rightarrow (2) Let E_{22}^* be any $\dot{N}_{eut}OS$ in \dot{N}_{eut}^Z . Then $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$ in \dot{N}_{eut}^X , by hypothesis. Since \dot{N}_{eut}^X is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha gaT_{1/2}space$, $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in \dot{N}_{eut}^X . Therefore $\dot{N}_{eut-cl}((\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*)) = (\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*)$. Now $\dot{N}_{eut-cl}(\dot{N}_{eut-int}(\dot{N}_{eut-cl}(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*))) \subseteq \dot{N}_{eut-cl}(\dot{N}_{eut-cl}(\dot{N}_{eut-cl}(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*))) = \dot{N}_{eut-cl}((\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*))$. This implies $\dot{N}_{eut-cl}(\dot{N}_{eut-int}(\dot{N}_{eut-cl}(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*))) \subseteq (\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*)$.

(2) \Rightarrow (1) Let E_{22}^* be a $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in \dot{N}_{eut}^Z . Then its complement E_{22}^{*c} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}OS$ in \dot{N}_{eut}^Z . By hypothesis, $\dot{N}_{eut-cl}(\dot{N}_{eut-int}(\dot{N}_{eut-cl}(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(E_{22}^{*c}))) \subseteq (\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(E_{22}^{*c})$. Hence $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(E_{22}^{*c})$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha CS$ in \dot{N}_{eut}^X . Since every $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha CS$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$, $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(E_{22}^{*c})$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$ in \dot{N}_{eut}^X . Hence $\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}$ is $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

3. Neutrosophic contra alpha generalized semi irresolute mappings

Definition 3.1. A mapping $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^X, \dot{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^Y, \dot{N}_{eut}^s)$ is called a Neutrosophic contra alpha generalized semi irresolute ($\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ irresolute in short) mapping if $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(E_{11}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$ in $(\dot{N}_{eut}^X, \dot{N}_{eut}^t)$ for every $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS E_{11}^*$ of $(\dot{N}_{eut}^Y, \dot{N}_{eut}^s)$.

Theorem 3.2. If $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^X, \dot{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^Y, \dot{N}_{eut}^s)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ irresolute mapping, then f is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping but the converse is not necessarily true.

Proof. Let \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} be a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ irresolute mapping. Let E_{11}^* be any $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in \dot{N}_{eut}^Y . Since every $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$, E_{11}^* is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$ in \dot{N}_{eut}^Y . By hypothesis, $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(E_{11}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in \dot{N}_{eut}^X . Hence \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Example 3.3. $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping $\not\rightarrow \dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ irresolute mapping.

Let $\dot{N}_{eut}^X = \{a_1^*, a_2^*\}$, $\dot{N}_{eut}^Y = \{a_3^*, a_4^*\}$, $E_{11}^* = \langle x, (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}), (\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}) \rangle$ and $E_{22}^* = \langle y, (\frac{7}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{5}), (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}) \rangle$. Then $\dot{N}_{eut}^t = \{0_{\dot{N}_{eut}}, E_{11}^*, 1_{\dot{N}_{eut}}\}$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^s = \{0_{\dot{N}_{eut}}, E_{22}^*, 1_{\dot{N}_{eut}}\}$ are $\dot{N}_{eut}Ts$ on \dot{N}_{eut}^X and \dot{N}_{eut}^Y respectively.

Define a mapping $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^X, \dot{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^Y, \dot{N}_{eut}^s)$ by $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_1^*) = a_3^*$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_2^*) = a_4^*$. Since $E_{22}^* = \langle y, (\frac{4}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{10}), (\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}) \rangle$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in \dot{N}_{eut}^Y , but $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(E_{22}^*) = \langle x, (\frac{4}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{10}), (\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}) \rangle$ is not a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$ in \dot{N}_{eut}^X . Therefore \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping but not a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ irresolute mapping.

Theorem 3.4. Let $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^X, \dot{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^Y, \dot{N}_{eut}^s)$ be a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ irresolute mapping, then $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f*^{-1}}(E_{11}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}GSCS$ in \dot{N}_{eut}^X for every $\dot{N}_{eut}OS E_{11}^*$ in \dot{N}_{eut}^Y .

Proof. Let \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} be a $\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ irresolute mapping. Let \hat{E}_{11}^* be any $\hat{N}_{eut}OS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$. Since every $\hat{N}_{eut}OS$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$, \hat{E}_{11}^* is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$. By hypothesis, $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(\hat{E}_{11}^*)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. This implies $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(\hat{E}_{11}^*)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}GSCS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$.

Example 3.5. Let $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_1^*) = a_3^*$ and $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*}(a_2^*) = a_4^*$, $\hat{E}_{11}^* = \langle x, (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}), (\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}) \rangle$ and $\hat{E}_{22}^* = \langle y, (\frac{7}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{5}), (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}) \rangle$. Then $\hat{N}_{eut}^t = \{0_{\hat{N}_{eut}}, \hat{E}_{11}^*, 1_{\hat{N}_{eut}}\}$ and $\hat{N}_{eut}^s = \{0_{\hat{N}_{eut}}, \hat{E}_{22}^*, 1_{\hat{N}_{eut}}\}$ are $\hat{N}_{eut}Ts$ on X and Y respectively. Define a mapping $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s)$. Then $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(\hat{E}_{11}^*)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}GSCS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$ for every $\hat{N}_{eut}OS$ $\hat{E}_{11}^* = \langle x, (\frac{7}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{5}), (\frac{3}{10}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{5}) \rangle$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$. But \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} is not a $\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ irresolute mapping. Since $\hat{E}_{22}^* = \langle y, (\frac{4}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{10}), (\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}) \rangle$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$ but $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(\hat{E}_{22}^*) = \langle x, (\frac{4}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{10}), (\frac{2}{5}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}) \rangle$ is not a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$.

Theorem 3.6. Let $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ irresolute mapping, then \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a Neutrosophic contra continuous mapping if $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha gaT_{1/2}$ space.

Proof. Let \hat{E}_{11}^* be a $\hat{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$. We know that every $\hat{N}_{eut}CS$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$, \hat{E}_{11}^* is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$. By hypothesis, $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(\hat{E}_{11}^*)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Since $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha gaT_{1/2}$ space, $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(\hat{E}_{11}^*)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}OS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Hence \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a Neutrosophic contra continuous mapping.

Theorem 3.7. If $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s)$ and $\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^d)$ are $\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ irresolute mapping, then $\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^d)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GS$ irresolute mapping.

Proof. Let \hat{E}_{11}^* be a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}$. Then $\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*-1}(\hat{E}_{11}^*)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$. Since \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ irresolute mapping, $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*-1}(\hat{E}_{11}^*))$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. That is $(\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(\hat{E}_{11}^*)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Hence $\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*}$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GS$ irresolute mapping .

Theorem 3.8. If $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ irresolute mapping and $\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^d)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mappings, then $\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^d)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Proof. Let \hat{E}_{11}^* be a $\hat{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}$. Then by hypothesis, $\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*-1}(\hat{E}_{11}^*)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$. Since \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\hat{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ irresolute mapping, $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*-1}(\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*-1}(\hat{E}_{11}^*))$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. That is $(\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(\hat{E}_{11}^*)$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GSCS$ in $\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Hence $\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*}$ is a $\hat{N}_{eut}\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Theorem 3.9. If $\hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s)$ is a $N\alpha GS$ irresolute mapping and $\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^s) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^d)$ is a $NC\alpha GS$ continuous mappings, then $\hat{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \hat{N}_{eut}^{f*} : (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\hat{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}, \hat{N}_{eut}^d)$ is a $NC\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Proof. Let E_{11}^* be a $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}$. Then by hypothesis, $\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*-1}(E_{11}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$. Since $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*}$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GS$ irresolute mapping, $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*-1}(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*-1}(E_{11}^*))$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. That is $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(E_{11}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Hence $\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*}$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Theorem 3.10. *Let $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^s)$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^s) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^d)$ be any two mappings. If the mapping $\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*}$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ irresolute mapping and X is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha gaT_{1/2}$ space, then*

- (1) $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$ for each $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}$.
- (2) $\dot{N}_{eut-cl}(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(Neu-int(E_{22}^*)) \subseteq (\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*)$ for each Neutrosophic set E_{22}^* of $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}$.

Proof. (1) Let E_{22}^* be a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}$. Then E_{22}^{*c} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}$. By hypothesis, E_{22}^{*c} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. This implies E_{22}^* is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. (2) Let E_{22}^* be any $\dot{N}_{eut}S$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}$ and $\dot{N}_{eut-int}(E_{22}^*) \subseteq E_{22}^*$. Then $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(\dot{N}_{eut-int}(E_{22}^*)) \subseteq (\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*)$. Since $\dot{N}_{eut-int}(E_{22}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}OS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}$, $\dot{N}_{eut-int}(E_{22}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$.

Therefore by hypothesis, $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(\dot{N}_{eut-int}(E_{22}^*))$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Since $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha gaT_{1/2}$ space, $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(\dot{N}_{eut-int}(E_{22}^*))$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Hence $\dot{N}_{eut-cl}((\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(\dot{N}_{eut-int}(B))) = (\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(\dot{N}_{eut-int}(E_{22}^*)) \subseteq (\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*)$. Therefore $\dot{N}_{eut-cl}((\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(\dot{N}_{eut-int}(E_{22}^*))) \subseteq (\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*)$ for each $\dot{N}_{eut}S$ E_{22}^* of $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}$.

Theorem 3.11. *If $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^s)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping and $\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^s) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^d)$ is a Neutrosophic continuous mappings, then $\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^d)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.*

Proof. Let E_{11}^* be a $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}$. Then by hypothesis, $\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*-1}(E_{11}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}$. Since $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*}$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping, $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*-1}(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*-1}(E_{11}^*))$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. That is $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(E_{11}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Hence $\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*}$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

Theorem 3.12. *Let $\dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^t) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^s)$ and $\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} : (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Y}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^s) \rightarrow (\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}, \dot{N}_{eut}^d)$ be any two mappings. Then the given conditions are equivalent if $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha gaT_{1/2}$ space.*

- (1) $\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*}$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha G$ continuous mapping.
- (2) $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*) \subseteq \dot{N}_{eut-int}(\dot{N}_{eut-cl}(\dot{N}_{eut-int}(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*)))$ for each $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ E_{22}^* of $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}$.

Proof. (1) \Rightarrow (2) Let E_{22}^* be a $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}$. By hypothesis, $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Since $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha gaT_{1/2}$ space, $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g^*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f^*})^{-1}(E_{22}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}OS$

in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Therefore $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(\hat{E}_{22}^*) = \dot{N}_{eut-int}((\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(\hat{E}_{22}^*))$. But $\dot{N}_{eut-int}((\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(\hat{E}_{22}^*)) \subseteq \dot{N}_{eut-int}(\dot{N}_{eut-cl}(\dot{N}_{eut-int}((\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(\hat{E}_{22}^*))))$. This implies $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(\hat{E}_{22}^*) \subseteq \dot{N}_{eut-int}(\dot{N}_{eut-cl}(\dot{N}_{eut-int}((\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(\hat{E}_{22}^*))))$ for every $\dot{N}_{eut}CS\hat{E}_{22}^*$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}$.

(2) \Rightarrow (1) Let \hat{E}_{22}^* be a $\dot{N}_{eut}CS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{Z}}$.

By hypothesis, $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(\hat{E}_{22}^*) \subseteq \dot{N}_{eut-int}(\dot{N}_{eut-cl}(\dot{N}_{eut-int}((\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(\hat{E}_{22}^*))))$. This implies $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(\hat{E}_{22}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha OS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$ and hence $(\dot{N}_{eut}^{g*} \circ \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*})^{-1}(\hat{E}_{22}^*)$ is a $\dot{N}_{eut}\alpha GSOS$ in $\dot{N}_{eut}^{\dot{X}}$. Therefore \dot{N}_{eut}^{f*} is a $\dot{N}_{eut}C\alpha GS$ continuous mapping.

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